

TIGRAY WATER WORKS STUDY, DESIGN AND SUPERVISION ENTERPRISE

GHOSTUDIO TRAINING MANUAL

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 General

The main embankment dam elements to be included during design process are fixing the dam height, dam crest, dam zooming, provision of necessary filter materials for both filtering and discharging purposes and analyzing the slope stability of both upstream and downstream slopes under different loading conditions. The various design elements indicated above can be done by following scientific and practically accepted designed principles available in various literatures and guide lines. Slopes for both upstream and downstream of an embankment dam can be adapted from different sources by considering the fill material, dam height and type of embankment dam. But this approach may lead to either uneconomical or unsafe structure, and hence to avoid this problem it is necessary to carryout slope stability analysis for dams.

Various analytical methods for evaluating the stability of slopes exist including charts and hand calculations. However, the methods of analysis should be selected according to the complexity of the slope and the data available to define the site conditions considering the time and costs. Therefore, the use of a reliable and verified slope stability analysis computer program is recommended for performing slope stability analyses where conditions are complex, where significant amounts of data are available, and where possible consequences of failure are significant. Computer programs provide a means for efficient and rapid detailed analysis of wide variety of slope geometry and load conditions. Among the many, GeoStudio software is presented here following the request made by the enterprise aiming at capacity building for design engineers.

1.2 Objectives

The main objective of this training is to introduce the trainee with design basics of earth fill dams and powerful computer program called GeoStudio 2007 for slope stability analysis.

- **Specific Objectives:**

The specific objectives of the training will include:

- To introduce the basic design elements of earth fill dams;
- To introduce slope stability analysis methods and analysis under different loading conditions;
- Familiar trainees with the fundamental of GeoStudio 2007 products i.e. SEEP/W and SLOPE/W;
- Introducing basic conceptual essences of slope stability and seepage analysis;
- Selection of input parameters (strength and permeability) for analysis and design; and
- Familiar trainees how to model, manipulate, extract outputs and interpret results from GeoStudio 2007.

1.3 Program Overview

GeoStudio is a product suit for geotechnical and geo-environmental modeling, broad enough to handle all modeling needs. It has got several components which are developed to model specific purposes. The products are SEEP/W, SLOPE/W, SIGMA/W, QUAKE/W, TEMP/W, CETRAN/W, AIR/W and VADASCO/W.

Most often slope stability is considered a 2D problem as 3D failure surfaces generally yield higher factors of safety. Common slope stability analysis procedures use the limit equilibrium method (LEM). The LEM assumes that when a slope fails, a soil mass is sliding on a failure surface. At failure, soil strength is fully mobilized along the failure surface. At the same time, the sliding mass is in static equilibrium. Description of the GeoStudio products selected for the training are briefly presented as follows.

1.3.1 SEEP/W

SEEP/W is a finite element software product that can be used to model the movement and pore-water pressure distribution within porous materials such as soil and rock. Its comprehensive formulation makes it possible to analyze both simple and highly complex

seepage problems. SEEP/W has application in the analysis and design for geotechnical, civil, hydro-geological and mining engineering projects.

1.3.1 SLOPE/W

SLOPE/W is a software product that uses limit equilibrium theory to compute the factor of safety of earth and rock slopes. SLOPE/W analyzes the stability of slip surfaces using vertical slice limit equilibrium methods (e.g. Bishop, Janbu, Spencer, GLE, etc.). Individual slip surfaces can be analyzed, or search methods can be applied to locate the critical slip surface for a given slope. Deterministic (safety factor) or probabilistic (probability of failure) analyses can be carried out.

The comprehensive formulation of SLOPE/W makes it possible to easily analyse both simple and complex slope stability problem using a variety of methods to calculate the minimum factor of safety and the critical slip surfaces.

SLOPE/W has application in the analysis and design for geotechnical, civil and mining engineering products. The methods available in *Slope/W* – GeoSlope are shown below.

Method	Moment Equilibrium	Force Equilibrium
Ordinary or Fellenius	Yes	No
Bishop's Simplified	Yes	No
Janbu's Simplified	No	Yes
Spencer	Yes	Yes
Morgenstern-Price	Yes	Yes
Corps of Engineers – 1	No	Yes
Corps of Engineers – 2	No	Yes
Lowe-Karafiath	No	Yes
Janbu Generalized	Yes (by slice)	Yes
Sarma – vertical slices	Yes	Yes

1.3.3 QUAKE/W

QUAKE/W is a geotechnical finite element software product for the dynamic analysis of earth structures subjected to earthquake shaking. The software can potentially be used for other types of geotechnical dynamic analyses but the software is primarily aimed at cases where the excitation arises from earthquakes.

A view that is gaining some prominence is that the most serious and significant deformation occurs after the earthquake shaking has stopped. This is referred to as post-earthquake

deformation, and can often lead to excessively large permanent deformation. Post-earthquake deformation is caused not so much by the inertial forces and motion, but by the re-distribution of excess pore-water pressures and the associated loss of shear strength. This is particularly true for man-made structures such as earth embankments.

The current version of QUAKE/W does not address permanent deformation. QUAKE/W is intended as the first step in a dynamic earthquake analysis. It is designed to do the dynamic part of the analysis and to compute the excess pore-water pressures that may be generated. Once the QUAKE/W analysis is complete, the resulting stresses and pore-water pressures can then be used in SLOPE/W (another software product in GEO-SLOPE Office) to analyze the stability aspects of the problem. This procedure is analogous to using static SIGMA/W stresses in SLOPE/W to evaluate stability.

SLOPE/W can use the QUAKE/W results to look at the variation in stability during the shaking and estimate the permanent deformation that may take place due to the inertial forces. SLOPE/W computes the factor of safety for each instance in time that QUAKE/W has saved results. This results in a factor of safety versus time plot for each slip surface.

1.3.4 SIGMA/W

SIGMA/W is a finite element software product that can be used to perform stress and deformation analyses of earth structures. Its comprehensive formulation makes it possible to analyze both simple and highly complex problems. For example, you can perform a simple linear elastic deformation analysis or a highly sophisticated nonlinear elastic-plastic effective stress analysis. When coupled with SEEP/W, (another GEO-SLOPE software product), it can also model the pore-water pressure generation and dissipation in a soil structure in response to external loads. SIGMA/W has application in the analysis and design for geotechnical, civil, and mining engineering projects.

Considering the relevance and objective of the proposed training SLOPE/W and SEEP/W, with basic theory and Real project exercises will be explained and covered in this training. Additional exercises can be covered based on data generated by the Enterprise for either existing or new projects.

2. SEEP/W 2007: Training Manual

SEEP/W is used to analyze the unconfined flow through an earth dam; and the results include total head contours, velocity vectors, and the location of the water table or zero pressure contour.

The approach to use when developing a numerical model in SEEP/W is, first draw the geometry; create and assign materials, create and assign boundary conditions and then finally, to review and fine-tune the finite element mesh. We will start by creating a new SEEP/W project from the start page of GeoStudio, once you click the new problem you will get a KeyIn Analysis dialog box.

2.1 Open GeoStudio

1. Select GeoStudio2007 from the Start Programs menu under the GEO-SLOPE folder or click GeoStudio short cut on the desktop.
2. Once GeoStudio has been opened, choose New from the File pull down menu, Click SEEP/W and KeyIn Analysis dialogue box will appear.

2.2 Selecting Analysis;

1. Click KEYIN analysis and then click add, select SEEP/W and Steady state from the drop down menu.
2. Adapt the default values and the name of analysis, and description as well. For example, you can name it: Steady-State Seepage Analysis and Description as SEEP/W Exercise.

2.3 Defining the Geometry

Before defining the Geometry, the Cross section of the problem should be ready in either of the following formats CAD, jpg, text, excel etc. formats.

1. For this exercise open the Shimta dam section .DWG in AutoCAD, select the material boundary you want to obtain its 2D coordinates, enter list in the command, press Enter Copy the list to text file; Repeat for the remaining boundaries and copy the texts to the text file. Arrange and save the point data.

Table: 2.1 Silient features of preliminary section

Description	Value	Unit	Remark
RBL	2508.5	masl.	
DSL	2524	masl.	
NPL	2540	masl.	
Hd	1.1	m	
MWL	2541.1	masl.	
DCL	2543.5	masl.	
Dam Height	35.0	m	
Dam Bottom Width	175.50	m	
Core Crest Level	2542.10	masl.	
Cut-off Trench BL	2503.5	masl.	
Dam U/S slope (mH:1V)	2.5		
Dam D/S slope (mH:1V)	2		
Dam Crest Length	6	m	
Core Crest Length	3	m	
Berm width	3	m	

Dam Cross Section at Center

Figure: 2.1 Dam Cross section at centre

- Importing points: choose Points from the KeyIn menu and the KeyIn points dialog box appears; Copy an excel dam section coordinate data and paste it by Right-clicking, you can also type the data in text box each time by clicking Add button, Click close.

KeyIn Points

ID	X (m)	Y (m)	Label
1	0	0	Point+Number
2	25	10	Point+Number
3	28	10	Point+Number
4	41.75	15.5	Point+Number
5	53	20	Point+Number
6	56	20	Point+Number
7	84.75	31.5	Point+Number
8	93.5	35	Point+Number
9	96.5	35	Point+Number
10	99.5	35	Point+Number
11	129.5	20	Point+Number
12	132.5	20	Point+Number
13	152.5	10	Point+Number
14	155.5	10	Point+Number
15	173.5	1	Point+Number
16	130.6	1	Point+Number
17	98	33.6	Point+Number
18	95	33.6	Point+Number
19	61.4	0	Point+Number
20	131.6	0	Point+Number
21	96.5	-5	Point+Number
22	94.5	-5	Point+Number
23	89.5	0	Point+Number
24	98.5	-5	Point+Number
25	103.5	0	Point+Number
26	175.5	0	Point+Number
27	-10	0	Point+Number
28	-10	-5	Point+Number
29	185.5	0	Point+Number
30	185.5	-5	Point+Number
31	-10	-15	Point+Number
32	185.5	-15	Point+Number
33	-10	31.5	Point+Number

Buttons: Add, Delete, Undo, Redo, Close

2.4 Draw the Problem;

When creating the numerical model, first draw the geometry; create and assign materials, Create and assign boundary conditions and then finally, to review and fine-tune the finite element mesh. The lines are considered objects, which can be adjusted or deleted using the modify objects command.

- Using the DRAW Regions Command Individual soil regions will be created by zooming and clicking to the points (coordinates) that will define the required Geometry. Click the left mouse button to create region points. Once the polygon region has been closed, you can either continue to draw additional regions, or you can exit the draw regions mode.

Region Name	Material	Region Points	Remark
Region 1	Shell	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19	
Region 2	Core	23,22,24,25,20,16,17,18,19	
Region 3	Filter	26,20,16,15	
Region 4	Soil Foundation	27,1,19,23,22,28,29,30,24,25,20,26	
Region 5	Rock Foundation	31,28,22,24,30,32	

2.5 Set the Working Area;

The working area is the size of the space available for defining the problem, in order to develop a numerical model, the working area should be set so that you can work at a convenient scale. The working area may be smaller, equal to or greater than the printer page. If the working area is larger than the printer page, the problem will be printed on multiple pages when the Zoom Factor is 1.0 or greater.

- Set working page size: choose Page from the Set menu and the Set Page dialog box appears; select the convenient Width and Height dimensions for your problem also click mm to set dimensions in SI unit. Then click Ok. For this exercise select the dimensions to Width = 1200mm and Height = 375mm

Tip: The Printer Page group box displays the name of the printer selected and the printing space available on one printer page. This information is presented to help you define a working area that will print properly ether in A3, A4...etc. formats.

4. Setting the scale: choose Units and Scale from the Set menu and the Set Units and Scale dialog box appears; The next step is to set the scale. The scale should be set such that the minimum and maximum extents in SLOPE/W match those required for the analysis. Define the x and y extents to find an approximate scale and then fine tune it so you have a 1:1 aspect ratio.

The geometry of the problem is defined as shown in Figure 2.1, for this problem Let us initially estimate the scale for both horizontal and vertical to 1:200 and minimum extents for X= -25 and Y= -25. Once the extents of the problem have been set, DEFINE computes the maximum x and y extents will then be automatically adjusted to reflect the scale you have selected. but make sure that calculate max. extents from scale and origin is ticked. Then click Ok.

- Set the Grid Spacing: choose Grid from the Set menu; a background grid of points will help you draw the problem. These points can be "snapped to" when creating the problem geometry in order to create points and lines with exact coordinates. A suitable grid spacing can be selected as per your requirement in this exercise provide 0.1 m Grid spacing. Make sure that display Grid and Snap to Grid are ticked.

- Set an axis: choose Axis from the Set menu and the Axis dialog box appears; On the Axis titles write Distance (m) in the Bottom X and Elevation (m) in the Left Y. Make sure that Left and Bottom Axis are ticked on display, axis numbers is also ticked. After you click Ok Set Axis size to fix the minimum X and Y and number of increments (spacing). For this exercise the starting origin will be (-15, -15) & Increments for X & Y set to be 20 & 5 m respectively. Sketch an axis: choose Axis from the Sketch menu or click sketch axis icon you will get a small cross that will be used for drawing the axis, the axis is drawn by moving the cursor from the bottom left corner and stretching it outward.

2.6 Creating materials;

Materials are first created and then assigned to geometry objects.

3. Click Materials on KEYIN to create material, click add Name it **core**, and select **saturated and un saturated** from the material model dropdown list and do the same for the rest materials.

2.7 Setting Material Property Functions;

In GeoStudio SEEP/W analysis there are two material functions to be defined, i.e. Hydraulic conductivity and Volumetric water content which are expressed as a function of metric suction. These material properties can be input manually as individual point or can be estimated using two estimation options, Using Grain-size estimation or Utilizing Sample function data base.

Grain-size estimation using D60 and D10 in GeoStudio

Sample Functions in GeoStudio

N.B

- Unless, the Transient Analysis (where pore water pressure varies with time) estimation of VWC is not necessary for steady state but it needs to estimate the Hydraulic conductivity function.
- In estimating, VWC, you can use Sample functions, if you don't have grain size data, but for Clay Soils Sample function should be utilized.
- The K, is fundamentally a function of VWC, always start by estimating the Volumetric Water Content function and estimate the Hydraulic Conductivity function.

- Liquid limit is used to correct for fine content when the Porosity is greater than 30% while determining VWC function from the Grain Size.
- Residual water content ranges from 5% to 10% of saturated water content.

Material	Sat. W. C. (Porosity)	Res. W. C.	Liquid Limit	Kx (m/s)	USC Classification	Remark
Core	0.43	0.1	46.05	5.76e-10		
Shell	0.4	0.05	39.5	1e-6		
Soil Foundation	0.36	0.1	42	5.5e-7		
Filter	0.35	0.05		5.5e-3		

Table 2.2 Data environment for Material Property Functions for SEEP/W

2.8 Setting the Volumetric water content function;

4. After creating a material on the KeyIn Material menu click the ellipses (...) to access KeyIn VWC function, Click Add Name: Clay VWC Function, Type: Vol. WC Data Point function, laboratory data can be pasted in to the dialog box if available.

5. Select the estimate button, select Sample functions method from Estimation method, write the value of the Saturated water content from the lab data on **table 2.2**, Select Clay on the Sample Materials, From the graph it is better to make the X to Log scale, then close, Associate the VWC function with defined material function.

2.9 Setting the hydraulic conductivity function;

- KeyIn Hydraulic Conductivity Function click the ellipses (...) to access KeyIn K function, Click Add Name: Clay Conductivity, Type: Hyd. K Data Point function, laboratory data can be pasted in to the dialog box if available.

7. Select the estimate button, select Van Genuchten from Estimation method, Select the material VWC assigned before on the Vol. Water Content Function, write the value of the K(m/s) at saturation from the lab data on **table 2.2**, write the Residual water content from Table3.1, K functions are highly nonlinear, therefore make log scale for both X and Y from the Graph, click close and Associate the K function with the Material.

2.10 Adding Material Property Functions;

8. We could now repeat the process for all materials in the domain either by cloning or by clicking add on the KeyIn Materials window.

2.11 Assigning the materials;

9. Choose materials from the Draw drop down menu to assign the material properties (hydraulic function) to the core soil. And do the same for the rest of materials. The materials can now be assigned to the geometry regions.

2.12 Fixing Boundary Conditions;

10. Boundary conditions are created and assigned in the same way materials are. Sometimes it can be helpful to sketch additional information on your geometry so you know where to define your boundary conditions.

Select Boundary Conditions from the DRAW menu. There are already two commonly used boundary conditions available for you to modify or use.

2.13 Assign New Boundary Conditions;

11. You can also create your own boundary condition. For this example, we need a boundary condition that will reflect the full reservoir level of 31.5 m. Click KeyIn boundary conditions to assign a boundary for a reservoir. Then click add button, add new hydraulic boundary condition, give name i.e. Reservoir Full Level = 31.5 m and change the color. Make sure that on the type pull down menu to Head (H) and insert the reservoir depth i.e. 31.5m in the action box.

2.14 Applying Boundary Conditions;

Once the boundary conditions have been created, you can then apply them to the region geometry.

12. A zero pressure boundary condition will be applied to the horizontal Filter, which is a geometry line. **Make sure that the select line clicked.**
13. Select the potential Seepage face from drop down menu, a potential seepage face boundary condition will be applied to the downstream face of the core, which is an edge. A potential seepage face is a special boundary condition that is used when you want the solver to locate the position of where a seepage face might develop.

14. To add the reservoir from sketch menu, select polyline and draw the upstream reservoir level starting from (-10, 31.5) to (84.75, 31.5). Fix the boundary by selecting Full Reservoir = 31.5 m, make sure that line is selected. Then click upstream face of the dam.

2.15 Reviewing the Finite Element;

Now that the geometry has been drawn, the material properties created and assigned and the boundary conditions applied, it's time to review the finite element.

15. You can view the finite element mesh using Draw: Mesh Properties. The meshing algorithm in SEEP/W is defaulted to use a global element. To make the mesh more finely discretized, type in a smaller global element size and the mesh will be updated automatically. While you can apply meshing constraints to individual geometry objects, it is often best to start with the default mesh and then constrain the mesh only if necessary.

The finite element mesh will disappear once you leave the DRAW: Mesh Properties view. If you wish to leave it on, you can click the “view mesh” icon on the view preferences toolbar.

2.16 Determining Flux Section;

One of the objectives of this analysis was to compute the amount of flow through the earth dam and foundation. To do this, we can use a flux section. Flux sections are used to identify elements where you want the software to compute and report the amount of flow crossing these elements during the solve process.

16. Draw: Flux Sections; Type the Section Number, click Ok button and Draw the flux section at one point, you may select at the center of the dam axis.

2.17 Solve and Contouring;

Now it's time to solve the problem.

17. Verify the input data by clicking Verify/Optimize icon.

18. The solver for SEEP/W can be launched by clicking on the “SOLVE” icon. Click the Start button to activate the solver.

19. You can view the results directly by clicking on the CONTOUR icon in the analysis toolbar. By default, the CONTOUR results will include velocity vectors, the location of the zero pressure contour and total head contours.

20. The flux section results can be viewed by selecting flux labels from the DRAW Menu. Clicking on the flux section will make the total flux value appear. This value is the total amount of flow past the flux section per unit length.

- 21.** Flow paths represent the path that a drop of water would travel from the reservoir through the dam and foundation. Draw a flow path by using the appropriate pull down menu and then click the cursor anywhere within the profile. You can remove a flow path by clicking on it a second time. It is important to remember that flow paths are not the same as flow lines.

2.18 Additional features;

- Remember, at any time you can change the way the CONTOUR information is presented by using the View Preferences pull down menu.
- You can also retrieve information from specific locations on the profile. Select VIEW: Result Information and then click on the location that you are interested in. If you hold the CTRL key down, you can gather information from several different locations.
- You can label your contours using DRAW: Contour Labels.
- There are many different types of parameters you can contour. Use DRAW: Contours to view some different results. Three default contour options are available, but you can also add other options to the list using the Add button.

2.19 Adding New Analysis;

One of the powerful features that's new to GeoStudio 2007 is the ability to run many different analyses within the same project file. The geometry is considered project specific, but you can change boundary conditions, material properties or even different types of analysis.

- 22.** One example might be to now use the SEEP/W computed pore-water pressures in a stability analysis using SLOPE/W. Click on KEYIN and analysis, select the SLOPE/W and from the dropdown menu select steady state seepage analysis from Parent and Parent analysis, from PWP conditions drop down button. Remember to give Name and Description of analysis.

Optionally, you could use the results from the steady-state simulation as a starting point for a transient simulation where you might model rapid drawdown of the reservoir. You can also include multiple analyses in a project file that do not depend on each other. It's a convenient way to explore different scenarios for the same geometry.

3. SLOPE/W 2007: Training Manual

This chapter introduces you to SLOPE/W by presenting the step-by-step procedures involved in analysing a simple slope stability problem. By executing each step in the sequence presented, you will be able to define a problem, compute the factors of safety, and view the results. By completing this exercise, you can quickly obtain an understanding of the features and operations of SLOPE/W. GeoStudio is a commercial software and it is provided with different capabilities based on the license requirements. For this training we will use the student version to explain the basics, which can simulate up to three materials at a time.

The approach to use when developing a numerical model in SLOPE/W is almost similar with that of SEEP/W i.e. draw the geometry. Create and assign materials, draw pore-water pressure conditions and draw the slip surface geometry, which will control the mode of failure you are going to analyse. The lines are considered objects, which can be adjusted or deleted using the modify objects command. Therefore, we can use the Geometry and materials already defined in SEEP/W or Start New, for this exercise it is preferred to use the SEEP/W exercise.

3.1 Using Regions and PWP Conditions from SEEP/W Software;

23. Open the previous SEEP/W file using normal window once you open it you will find the region which was created in the SEEP/W Exercise, make sure that to change your file name. Save it with different file name. Example, SLOPE-W Exercise. Switch to DEFINE view to define the current analysis.

3.2 KeyIn Analysis;

24. Click the KeyIn menu, on the KeyIn Dialog box click the add button to select the type of analysis, in this case select the SLOPE/W Analysis and then Limit equilibrium.
25. You need to give Name of Analysis and Description, I.e. Slope Stability Analysis and exercise respectively for this training.
26. Select Parent Analysis if you have or it will be none as default if you don't have made analysis for this exercise select SEEP-W Exercise as Parent.
27. You need to identify what method of analysis you are going to use- Select **Morgenstern-Price**
28. In the settings dialog box; Ensure that Half-Sine function is being applied on the side function.
29. Under the pore water pressure (PWP) Condition, select Parent Analysis.
30. Under the slip surface tab, select direction of movement left to right for d/s slope and slip surface option as entry and exit method to search for the critical slip surface.
31. For the Factor of safety and advance Tab you use the default as it is. Some of the functions can be activated for licensed software. Finally, you may click close after finishing the analysis setting.

3.3 Creating materials;

32. Choose materials from the DRAW: dropdown menu; Materials are first created and then assigned to geometry objects. Click on KEYIN: to create a material. Add a new material, name it and select a strength model from the drop down list. You can use the tab key to move between the edit boxes. You may put the name as Shell, material model as Mohr-Coulomb and Basic Material Properties from the Table below

Table: Material Properties data for SLOPE/W

Material Type	C, (kpa)	Φ_u , (Deg.)	Y, (KN/m ³)	Remark
Core	48	15.9	18.8	
Shell	26	37	17	
Filter	9.67	38.66	21	
Foundation	15.67	34.22	18	

33. To create remaining material, you have choices; you can either add, or you can clone the existing material. Follow the same procedure to add more materials and finally click close to end inserting the soil properties.

3.4 Assigning materials;

The materials can now be assigned to the individual geometry regions.

34. Choose materials from Draw drop down menu. Then click the material to get the following dialog box. Then drag the respective material type and paste on respective region. The color for the region can be done by drop down menu from assign.

3.5 Slip Surface Fixing;

Earlier we selected the entry and exit method to control the location of the trial slip surfaces.

- 35. Choose Slip Surfaces from the DRAW menu. Use the cursor to define “zones” where the slip surface will enter and then exit the cross section. For downstream slope analysis, the Entry range is Left side and the Exit range is Right side. But for upstream slope the Entry will be the Right side and the Exit will be the Left side. Click Apply and Done.

3.6 Earth quake acceleration Coefficients;

- 36. To analysis the stability of the model considering seismic loading condition, appropriate seismic coefficients should be fixed based on the location zone of the structures. Click KeyIn and Seismic Loading, type the proper coefficients.

3.7 Viewing Input Data;

Now The Problem Definition has been completed. You need to double check your input in different ways.

37. Select object information from the VIEW pull down menu. Click within any region to review the soil properties for that particular region. You can also view the information for any other geometric object.

Another way to review your input parameters is to use the DRAW: Contours feature available within DEFINE. You can contour various parameters such as soil properties and pore-water pressures. Notice that when you define a piezometric line in SLOPE/W, the software considers the pore-water pressures to be hydrostatic both below and above the piezometric line. You can also label the contours.

You can go back to viewing the soil colors by using VIEW: Preferences from the drop down list, or using the appropriate preferences icon.

3.8 Verifying Input Data;

38. Choose Verify from the TOOLS drop down list and SLOPE/W will run a number of Checks to see if there are any errors or warnings.

3.9 Solve and Contour;

39. Click on the SOLVE icon found on the Current Analysis Toolbar. Select the start button to activate the solver. In the solver window you will see the computed factors of safety for each of the various methods. Click the start button to run the simulation. When the simulation is done correctly the status will be changed to Solved.

40. Click on the CONTOUR icon in the current analysis toolbar to review the results, the critical slip surface appears along with the critical factor of safety.

41. Use the Draw: Slip Surfaces command to bring up a dialogue box that summarizes the factors of safety for all the different slip surfaces that were analyzed. When you click on any single slip surface, you will cause both the slip surface and the corresponding factor of safety to appear in the CONTOUR window.

42. You can also review the slice force information for the most critical slip surface. Move the cursor inside any particular slice and click the left mouse button to select the slice. The force information can be copied and pasted directly into a report or spreadsheet.

Although we told the program to use the Morgenstern-Price method of analysis, results were also obtained for three other methods including Ordinary, Bishop and Janbu. You

can look at the results obtained for these methods by using the drop down menu or through the Method toolbar.

43. It is often helpful to look at how parameters vary across the slip surface. To create a graph, choose Graph from the Draw Menu. There are many different types of graphs that can be developed, including a plot of pore-water pressures across the slip surface. Both the graph and the raw data can be copied from SLOPE/W and pasted into a report or a spreadsheet for further analysis.

44. By default, the location of the critical slip surface is shown in CONTOUR; however, you can also view the location of the other slip surfaces that were analyzed. Choose Preferences from the View menu. Select the number of slip surfaces that you would like to view simultaneously. The slip surfaces for the 10 lowest factors of safety are now drawn on the profile.

45. Sometimes it is helpful to think in terms of a failure “zone” as opposed to a specific slip surface location. A safety map can be drawn on the profile to indicate a zone where slip surfaces with very similar factors of safety could develop.

Choose safety map from Draw drop down menu. Click Apply on the draw safety map dialog box.

3.10 Slope/W Analysis for U/S Slope;

The u/s slope Analysis can be done as of d/s slope except the following adjustments. Follow the same steps from 14 to 36. While doing this we need to change the current window in define and save as new file name i.e. upstream slope analysis for steady state or sudden drawdown or during construction.

- 46.** Open the Previous SLOPE/W Analysis File on Step 14
- 47.** Select Parent to None on Step 17
- 48.** Adjustment on the Entry and Exit of Slip Surfaces; the entry and exit boundary for slip surfaces in step 21, should be adjusted to Right to Left and change the direction of movement from Right to Left. Before Setting New Boundary make sure that you clear the previous boundaries set for the downstream slope.
- 49.** Adjustment on the Pore water Pressure; keyIn analysis dialog box, pore water pressure (PWP) Condition, select piezometric line in step 20. And Choose pore-water pressure from the DRAW menu. Add the piezometric line to the materials and then draw the line on the profile, the coordinates of the piezometric line should be pasted .for better accuracy.

The pore-water pressure conditions can be then defined by a single piezometric line. If you are modelling a partially submerged slope, the weight of the water will be automatically included in the analysis. A blue shaded zone will appear together with water force arrows which show that the resulting water force will be applied normal to the ground surface line.

3.11 Generating Report;

- 50.** Select Report from the View menu. Once you save the report file, your default word processing program will open with a generated report for both your input and output. You can now insert pictures, apply style templates or add and delete data.

Slope Stability Analysis

Report generated using GeoStudio 2007, version 7.10. Copyright © 1991-2008 GEO-SLOPE International Ltd.

File Information

Created By: [Girmay](#)
Revision Number: [174](#)
Last Edited By: [Girmay](#)
Date: [9/28/2017](#)
Time: [2:26:28 AM](#)
File Name: [Slope Stability Analysis.gsz](#)
Directory: [C:\Users\user\Desktop\](#)
Last Solved Date: [9/28/2017](#)
Last Solved Time: [2:26:44 AM](#)

Project Settings

Length(L) Units: [meters](#)
Time(t) Units: [Seconds](#)
Force(F) Units: [kN](#)
Pressure(p) Units: [kPa](#)
Strength Units: [kPa](#)
Unit Weight of Water: [9.807 kN/m³](#)

3.12 Help Function;

51. If at any time you need help with understanding a dialogue box, you can click on the question mark in the top left corner to access the on-line help or use F1 on your keyboard. You can also switch to the Analysis Start Page which has PDF copies of all the engineering books for GeoStudio under the documentation section. These books are very helpful in describing the features in the software and the theory behind them. You can also search through the examples database using specific keywords. When you are done, you can return to your analysis by clicking on the analysis list.

We have reached to the end of this introductory lesson. Not all of the powerful features of SLOPE/W have been used or discussed during this lesson. Specific details about each command are given in the on-line help and in the supporting documentation for SLOPE/W.